

Review

Moral Sensitivity, Ethical Experiences and Promotion of the Civility of Staff Nurses

Hameeda M. Aljanabi¹, Robin Maarman¹, Masoma A. Kehlini², Ola Mousa^{3*}

Abstract

¹Nursing Profession Development
Department, Dammam Medical
Complex, Dammam Health
Networking

²Beder Primary Health Care Center,
Dammam Health Networking

³College of Applied Medical Sciences,
King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
olaessam1977@yahoo.com

Nursing is built on a comprehensive concept and an ethical commitment to protect and maintain a patient's dignity and integrity. However, as a result of technical developments and medical progress, healthcare is rapidly evolving. Nurse burnout and ethical inconsideration occur from working under time restrictions and with a lot of responsibility, which restricts nurses' ability to act ethically and morally in customized treatment scenarios. The nursing code of ethics is a guide for "carrying out nursing responsibilities in a manner consistent with quality in nursing care and the ethical obligations of the profession." The following is a review paper on moral sensitivity, ethical experiences, and the promotion of the civility of staff nurses. The paper provides a summary of other research papers on the topic, historic and contemporary authors uphold various ethical experiences including the privacy and confidentiality of patients and the ability of nurses to make moral decisions.

Keywords: Civility of Staff, Clients, Dilemmas, Ethical Experiences, Moral Sensitivity, Nursing Ethics

INTRODUCTION

The nursing profession requires nurses to provide continuous holistic care for not only the sick but also the disabled and dying individuals. Lack of moral sensitivity in clinical practice threatens the quality of professional healthcare performance. Nurses assume the responsibility of promoting the health of patients, their families, and the entire community. Also, nurses play a significant role in health care research, support of patients, management, policy writing, and decision making (Kamali et al., 2019). While working, nurses practice civility, which includes teamwork and actions that demonstrate respect for others and help them feel valued. However, the present health sector, along with an exceedingly challenging clinical setting, presents a host of complicated ethical issues that necessitate the development of strong moral perceptions and abilities in health providers. Ethics has always been an element of

the nursing program. According to Yeom et al. (2017), many efforts have been made to improve ethical education in nursing schools in order to better prepare incoming healthcare practitioners to be ethical and socially responsible, as well as deal with ethical concerns and dilemmas that may arise in the future. The following review paper intended to delve into the idea of moral sensitivity, ethical experiences, and the promotion of civility among staff nurses.

Moral Sensitivity

Moral sensitivity in nursing means understanding the patient's vulnerability and being aware of the moral implications of one's decisions in any given situation. From this perspective, it would be a personal culture that

guides decision-making, involving an emotional response through a cognitive process that guides moral action and can involve moral tensions (Lütznén et al., 1994)). Moral sensitivity in the health sector is frequently debated in the literature globally. Kamali et al., (2019) discuss professional fundamentals with four components: interaction with clients, relationship development, patient satisfaction, and moralism. The authors believe in obligations' fulfillment, commitment to high standard guidelines, preserving responsibility, and integrity and dignity of the patient. However, nurses may face a significant number of moral issues during this process, including those associated with patient rights protection, nurses' value systems, nurses' constrained ability to meet acceptable moral obligations, organizational objection, systemic coercion, institutional revenue considerations, financial issues that may prevent a client from getting medical attention. Informed consent, a shared pool of scarce resources, differing perspectives among clinicians on medical diagnosis and services, and delivery of medical care for terminally ill people are considered.

According to Kraaijeveld et al. (2021), moral sensitivity not only include a personal decision on the right course of action but also the ability to understand the perspectives of other stakeholders. Nurses must be competent in moral decision-making and the governance of a variety of moral concerns in healthcare situations in order to practice moral sensitivity in the healthcare profession. Moreover, moral sensitivity is an essential element of a physician's credibility when caring for patients requiring their professional, and medical services. Arslan & Calpbini, (2018) think that when pediatric nurses act with a considerable level of moral sensitivity, they promote professionalism while impacting the quality of care they deliver to patients. Pediatric nurses ascribe the majority of their ethical issues to nursing shortages and a lack of understanding and conduct regarding professional ethical norms. Therefore, moral sensitivity is important for resolving ethical issues and justifying acts, including preventing ethical challenges and disagreements (Lütznén et al., 1995).

Logically, the high-quality clinical practice requires technical training and command of technological advances, but also congruent moral reasoning based on their own moral principles to guide them in their professional performance (Piaget, 1977). Healthcare workers in Saudi Arabia come from a multinational, multicultural with different educational backgrounds. Healthcare providers are currently confronted with moral dilemmas such as patient rights, economic equalization, and patient confidentiality in the kingdom. According to Cerit and Dinç (2013), one of the most common problems was that clinicians were under pressure from patients and family members, hence, resulting in unnecessary diagnoses and procedures. Converting, a shortage of resources contributed to the discontinuation of important therapies. Consequently, Saudi Arabian nurses

encounter a moral dilemma as they are required to have a spontaneous understanding of the client's susceptible situation and provide ultimate care despite the challenges (Almutairi et al., 2019). The patient-physician interaction is challenged because nurses have to be sensitive to moral matters and respect the patient's rights. Therefore, moral sensitivity is a key characteristic of caregivers, as it helps in making moral decisions.

Ethical Experiences

Nurses, physicians, and other medical workers encounter complex ethical issues in their work globally with substantial psychological consequences. These difficulties are frequently the result of judgments that with their principles, beliefs, and the practice essential for offering competent, timely, attentive, and ethical treatment (Almutairi and Rondney, 2013). All healthcare providers depend on their ethics to define what actions are in conflicting situations. Family traditions and culture, history, spirituality, societal norms and rules, and schooling influence the development of morals. According to Abbasi et al. (2014), significant advancements in medical research and contemporary technologies have fueled an ever-increasing demand for ethical debate. Critical thinking abilities are crucial in shaping and supporting the vibrant and evolving society of the twenty-first century. According to Muramatsu et al. (2019), medical ethics are a critical part of decision-making in the healthcare industry. Nurses, as healthcare providers, must demonstrate a high level of true ethical skills and must respect the norms and values of the patients.

Obtaining informed consent can be a tough ethical experience for nurses. A dilemma can occur when the client and family are not well informed or do not appreciate the medications that are being used on them. In KSA, nurses with different cultural and religious backgrounds encounter various ethical experiences with patients of Muslim religion (Halligan, 2006). This is because the attitudes and values of Islamic patients have an impact on their health care in several ways as viewed by expatriate nurses. Patients in Saudi Arabia globally are more likely to comply with a care plan resulting in improved outcomes if they feel supported and trust their medical professionals. Nurses encounter various ethical problems related to patient privacy. Incorrect practices could result in legal actions resulting in harsh punishments for healthcare providers. The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) safeguards the privacy of patients' medical records, thus there are strict guidelines and procedures in place (Spekkink & Jacobs, 2021). Nurses must respect their client's interests and make decisions that are in their best interests. According to Ganz et al. (2015), patient autonomy, or the ability of patients to make decisions

about their own treatment without being affected by personal or cultural beliefs, is a basic nursing value that all healthcare workers should uphold.

The collective choice is a far more ethical approach to patient care today than it was in the past when health care providers had unlimited authority over inpatient care. Individual freedom is increased by shared patient decision-making, which allows patients and physicians to collaborate to make informed decisions about their care (Amiri et al., 2019). Patients and health providers can have open discussions regarding a client's history, values, ideas, and culture through shared decision-making, resulting in a more trusting connection between patients and clinicians. Thus, patients' education is fundamentally important (Lingis, 2009).

Promoting Civility of Staff Nurses

In a nursing environment, civility involves actions that demonstrate respect for others. Civility is demonstrated in a multi-industry environment allowing individuals workforce, autonomy, and value. In nursing and health care, civil learning settings based on caring are critical for developing hope, compassion, and progressive impact on clients. Ackerman-Barger et al. (2021) believe that civility permits and fosters civil debate, particularly when opposing viewpoints are presented. This is especially crucial in today's health service, since eliminating health inequities and prejudiced care practices are necessary, and candid and uncomfortable dialogues among professionals are required (Clark, 2019).

Despite fostering a paradoxical culture of being caring and trusted, when new nurses join the workforce, they frequently encounter an unwelcoming setting. In the book, *Toxic Nursing, Managing Bullying, Bad Attitudes, and Total Turmoil*, several incoming nurses report being ridiculed, disparaged, bullied, and humiliated instead of being coached and fostered (Dellasega, 2020). Nurses and nurse instructors have allowed a culture in which they are competitors rather than advocates of one another.

While analyzing the cause of incivility in learning and nursing practice, Robertson (2012) states that psychologically unhealthy response to stressful conditions, time management challenges, role conflict, or economic or medical concerns are all possible causes. Ultimately, the community needs well-functioning health workers who are driven by kindness and civility to fulfill the ever-changing demands of clients, relatives, and the community. Ackerman-Barger, Dickinson, & Martin (2021) suggest that nurses must take responsibility for their actions and change their habits. Apologizing, becoming more or less authoritative, slowing, and not responding in rage are some of these behaviors to be changed. Setting an example, being approachable, and having good intentions are all examples of behavioral

change. In addition to regulating and reducing incivility, communication is a helpful method. Open, direct, and honest communication, as well as ensuring privacy when conducting dialogues about incivility instead of pointing someone out publicly, are examples of ways of communicating that might encourage an environment of civility. Taking perspective, listening, and seeking evidence before developing judgments is another important component of communication (Conner Black, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Overall, while technological improvements and medical services have improved patient care and given consumers more power, they have also generated ethical questions. In the field of healthcare coverage, these ethical considerations have become increasingly significant over time. Ethics is a set of moral rules, beliefs, and practices that govern ideas such as risks and rewards, good and evil, and right and wrong, as well as how these concepts manifest themselves in individual and group behavior relationships. Moral sensitivity in healthcare is defined as the ability to detect an ethical dilemma and comprehend the ethical implications of a patient's decisions, according to the research. On the other hand, civility refers to the acts of showing respect to others in an organization. Referring to different pieces of literature by various authors, the paper presents different ideas and reviews on ethical experiences, moral sensitivity and civility in a nursing environment. In conclusion, this article establishes a connection between the ethical experiences of nurses, moral sensitivity and civility in the workforce. Therefore, it is recommended to promote civility, address ethical concerns and promote the delivery of ethical care to patients, their family members, and the entire community.

REFERENCES

- Abbasi M, Nejad Sarvari N, Kiani M, Borhani F, Bazmi S, Tavaokoli SN, Rasouli H (2014). Moral distress in physicians practicing in hospitals affiliated to medical sciences universities. *Iranian Red Crescent Med. J.* 16(10).
- Ackerman-Barger K, Dickinson JK, Martin LD (2021). Promoting a Culture of Civility in Nursing Learning Environments. *Nurse Educator*, 46(4), 234-238.
- Almutairi AF, Rodney P (2013). Critical cultural competence for culturally diverse workforces: toward equitable and peaceful health care. *Advances in Nursing Science*, 36(3), 200-212.
- Almutairi AF, Salam M, Adlan AA, Alturki AS (2019). Prevalence of severe moral distress among healthcare providers in Saudi Arabia. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 12, 107.
- Amiri E, Ebrahimi H, Vahidi M, Asghari JM, Namdar AH (2019). Relationship between nurses' moral sensitivity and the quality of care. *Nursing ethics*, 26(4), 1265-1273.

- Arslan FT, Calpbinici P (2018). Moral sensitivity, ethical experiences and related factors of pediatric nurses: a cross-sectional, correlational study. *Acta Bioethica*, 24(1), 9-18.
- Cerit B, Dinç L (2013). Ethical decision-making and professional behaviour among nurses: a correlational study. *Nursing ethics*, 20(2), 200-212.
- Clark CM (2019). Fostering a culture of civility and respect in nursing. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 10(1), 44-52.
- Conner Black, A. (2019). Promoting Civility in Healthcare Settings. *Int. J. Childbirth Edu.* 34(2).
- Dellasega C (2020). *Toxic nursing: Managing bullying, bad attitudes, and total turmoil*. Sigma Theta Tau.
- Ganz FD, Wagner N, Toren O (2015). Nurse middle manager ethical dilemmas and moral distress. *Nursing Ethics*, 22(1), 43-51.
- Halligan P (2006). Caring for patients of Islamic denomination: critical care nurses' experiences in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 15(12), 1565-1573.
- Kamali F, Yousefy A, Yamani N (2019). Explaining professionalism in moral reasoning: a qualitative study. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 10, 447.
- Kraaijeveld MI, Schilderman J. B. A. M., van Leeuwen E (2021). Moral sensitivity revisited. *Nursing ethics*, 28(2), 179-189.
- Lingis A (2009). The fundamental ethical experience *Radical Passivity* (pp. 81-93): Springer.
- Lützn K, Nordin C, Brolin G (1994). Conceptualization and instrumentation of nurses' moral sensitivity in psychiatric practice. *Int. J. Methods in Psychiatric Res.*
- Lützn K, Nordström G, Evertzon M (1995). Moral sensitivity in nursing practice. *Scandinavian J. Caring Sci.* 9(3), 131-138.
- Piaget J (1977). El criterio moral en el niño (The moral judgement of the child). *Barcelona: Fontanella. (Original: 1932)*.
- Robertson JE (2012). Can't We ALL JUST GET ALONG? A Primer on Student Incivility in Nursing Education. *Nursing education perspectives*, 33(1), 21-26.
- Spekkink A, Jacobs G (2021). The development of moral sensitivity of nursing students: A scoping review. *Nursing ethics*, 28(5), 791-808.
- Yeom HA, Ahn SH, Kim SJ (2017). Effects of ethics education on moral sensitivity of nursing students. *Nursing ethics*, 24(6), 644-652.